

ITA212, a lowland variety, also yields well in the high rainfall uplands. But it is susceptible to grain discoloration (left). Silica greatly reduced the disease (right).

goethite. Annual rainfall averages 2,500 mm.

Silica as sodium silicate was applied before sowing at 400 kg/ha. Control and treated plots received 60-26-50 kg NPK/ha.

Disease intensity was markedly reduced on silica-treated plots (see table). The greatest effect was in reducing grain discoloration (see figure) and neck blast. Varieties differ in inherent resistance to these diseases; generally, semidwarfs are most susceptible. However, all varieties tested benefited from silica application. □

White leaf streak disease on rice in India

D.K. Nayak, H.S. Chakrabarti, and A. Pal, Rice Research Station (RRS), Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

White leaf streak disease was first reported by Deighton and Shaw in Papua New Guinea in 1960. The causal organism was designated as *Rumularia oryzae*. Subsequently, the fungus was renamed *Mycovellosiella oryzae* (Deighton & Shaw) Deighton. In India *Mycovellosiella* (= *Ramularia*) was recorded on several dicotyledonous plants. Until now there has been no report of the occurrence of this genus on cereals except for sorghum in India.

The disease was noticed in the ricefields of RRS Chinsurah, in Sep-Oct 1984. Pronounced symptoms appeared on cv. Ratna in Oct during the milk to soft dough stage. The disease was again

recorded in March 1985 but at lower severity.

Initial spots on the leaves are 0.5-2.5 mm long and 0.5-1.0 mm wide, oblong, white to creamish white, delimited by narrow brown margins,

Cellular inclusions in rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)-infected rice

F. C. Sta. Cruz and H. Hibino, IRRI

GSV-infected TN 1 plants were collected 1 mo after inoculation for electron microscope observation. Ultrathin sections showed an association of two types of inclusions in GSV-infected plants. No similar structures were observed in healthy plants.

Fibrils grouped in bundles were abundant in mesophyll and phloem cells. The fibrillar inclusions were free either in the nucleus or in the cytoplasm

1. Fibrillar inclusions (fi) in nucleus (n) and cytoplasm of a mesophyll cell (35,000X). m = mitochondria.

2. Tubular inclusions (ti) associated with tiny particles in a sieve tube of GSV-infected rice leaf (35,000X). m = mitochondria. cw = cell wall. st = sieve tube.

amphigenous, and interveinal. They spread basipetally from the leaf tips in a linear manner. The spots gradually coalesce and form white streaks on both surfaces of the leaves. □

(Fig. 1) or bounded with membrane in the cytoplasm. Similar inclusions were also found in vacuole and chloroplasts.

Another type of inclusion observed in the sieve tube consisted of tubular structures associated with particles 18 nm in diameter (Fig. 2). The occurrence of tubular structures was less frequent than that of fibrillar inclusions.

Similar fibrillar inclusions were observed in plants infected with maize stripe virus, rice stripe virus, and rice hoja blanca virus. Those viruses are similar to GSV in morphology and vector-virus interactions. The four can be classified in the same group. □

Effect of neem oil on tungro (RTV) infection in susceptible and resistant varieties

K.E.A. Aiyathan and P. Narayanasamy, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

RTV-susceptible and resistant cultivars were inoculated using 1, 3, and 5 viruliferous green leafhoppers (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* per plant. Neem

Effect of neem oil on RTV infection in susceptible and resistant varieties inoculated using different numbers of insects. Coimbatore, India.